

NOTES

Oxomolybdenum(V) Complexes with 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole

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COMPLEXES of various metal ions with 2-(2'-pyridyl)-benzimidazole (PBzH) are known¹⁻⁶. In present paper, we report the preparation and characterisation of complexes of oxomolybdenum(V) with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared as reported in previous paper¹. The starting complexes $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ were prepared as reported in literature⁷.

$(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$, ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$): $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ (~10 g) was dissolved in concentrated HCl (48% HBr) (40-50 ml) and treated with 1:1 molar ratio of PBzH dissolved in hot concentrated HCl/HBr. From the resulting solutions, crystalline salts of pentahalooxomolybdenum(V) separated gradually. The products were filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed with concentrated cold acid and dried in a desiccator over KOH.

$[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_3]$, ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$): $(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ (~5.0 g) was refluxed in dry methanol or propanol (40-50 ml) for ~1 h. The compound slowly went into solution from which brick-red compound separated out gradually. It was filtered, washed with dry methanol and dried as above.

$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{X}_4]$, ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$): $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ (~3-4 g) was dissolved in 95% ethanol (30-40 ml) and refluxed with 1:1 molar ratio of ligand on a steam-bath for 1 h. The resulting solution on concentration and cooling gave brick-red or brown precipitate. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

The results of elemental analyses and magnetic moment values at room temperature (303-5K) are given in Table 1.

Reflectance spectra of the solid complexes were determined on a Hilger and Watts UV Spek H700 spectrophotometer using MgCO_3 as standard. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 and 571 spectrophotometers and magnetic susceptibility by Gouy method as reported earlier⁸.

Results and Discussion

The pentahalo salts $(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$) at reflux temperature, in dry methanol, ethanol etc. undergo dehydrohalogenation reaction forming trihalo complexes, $[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_3]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$). However, in hydrated ethanol, oxobridged dinuclear complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{X}_4]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$) are formed. These oxobridged complexes can be reconverted into original mononuclear complexes, $[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_3]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$) on refluxing them with concentrated HCl/HBr. The complex salts $(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$) and trihalo complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_3]$ are paramagnetic while oxobridged complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{X}_4]$ are either diamagnetic or feebly paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values of $[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_3]$ ($X = \text{Cl or Br}$) are found in the range 1.65-1.69 B.M. which fall in the range of values shown by mononuclear oxomolybdenum(V) complexes⁹⁻¹⁰. The diamagnetism of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes possessing

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Spectral band positions (cm^{-1})		
			Mo	N	Halogen	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}(1)$	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow \text{E}(11) + \text{L} - \text{M}$
$(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$	Yellowish green	1.65	19.81 (19.72)	8.52 (8.64)	86.72 (86.44)	13 700mb	19 610m	22 780m
$(\text{PBzH})\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	Brown	1.63	13.43 (13.54)	6.10 (5.98)	56.61 (56.98)	14 080wb	20 890s	—
$[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{Cl}_3]$	Brick red	1.69	23.31 (23.20)	9.98 (10.16)	25.61 (25.72)	18 930mb	19 610m	24 390sh
$[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{Br}_3]$	Brick red	1.65	17.48 (17.54)	7.73 (7.68)	44.12 (43.84)	14 290sb	19 610m	24 390sh
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{Cl}_4]$	Reddish brown	Dia.	24.80 (24.85)	10.72 (10.88)	18.46 (18.97)	13 890wb	19 610m	22 730m
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{Br}_4]$	Reddish brown	0.84	19.52 (20.21)	8.61 (8.84)	88.51 (83.65)	—	—	—

* Temp. = 303-5 K.

s=strong; w=weak, m=medium; sh=shoulder; b=broad.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8^{4+}$ species is quite common as explained by Cotton and Curtis¹¹. The feeble paramagnetism of complex $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{Br}_4]$ can be attributed to bulky volume of the bonded ligand molecule. In

this case, the angle of twist of $\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}$ bond may be greater than $\pi/4$ due to bulky volume of the bromine which causes incomplete pairing of spins of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8^{4+}$ species¹¹.

Both mono- and di-nuclear complexes display electronic reflectance bands at 13 330-14 300, 19 610-20 800 and 22 390-24 400 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}(\text{I})$, ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$ and ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}(\text{II}) + \text{C}-\text{T}$ transitions, respectively, similar to ligand field bands of octahedral molybdenum(V) complexes¹²⁻¹⁴.

Ir spectra: From the studies of ir spectra of PBzH and its complexes with metal ions, the coordination of the ligand has been suggested from tertiary pyridine nitrogen of benzimidazole part^{15,16}. The N-H stretching mode of PBzH (3 249 cm^{-1}) is shifted to lower frequency only by 5-30 cm^{-1} in complexes but raised to higher frequency in complex salt $(\text{PBzH})_2\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_6]$ by 30 cm^{-1} suggesting that NH nitrogen is not involved in coordination. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ of PBzH (1 638 cm^{-1}) is shifted to lower frequency in complexes suggesting the coordination of ligand through tertiary pyridine nitrogen of benzimidazole part¹⁶. The pyridine ring breathing mode of vibration of ligand (996 cm^{-1}) is raised to higher frequency (5-25 cm^{-1}) which has been taken to be diagnostic of the coordinated pyridine nitrogen^{15,16}.

The complexes $(\text{PBzH})_2\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_6]$ and $[\text{MoO}(\text{PBzH})\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) display strong and sharp $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ stretch at 990-975 cm^{-1} while the dinuclear complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8(\text{PBzH})_2\text{X}_4]$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) exhibit $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ as strong and broad band at ~ 965 cm^{-1} . The observed order of wave number and nature of $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ vibration are in good agreement with $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ occurring in oxomolybdenum(V) complexes containing MoO^{8+} and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8^{4+}$ species^{17,18}. Due to a number of ligand vibrations

between 850 and 650 cm^{-1} the $\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}$ vibration could not be located definitely (the region 800-650 cm^{-1} is the range of vibration^{17,18}). In far-infrared region, the ligand and its complexes display a number of bands between 600 and 400 cm^{-1} . The new ir bands located at 370-300 cm^{-1} have been tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Mo-X}}$ in these complexes¹⁹.

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Studies on Quaternary Complexes of some Rare Earth Metals

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OUR recent studies¹⁻³ on quaternary complex formation of lanthanide ions indicated that inspite of being high electropositive in nature, the lanthanides are capable of extending their coordination sphere to acquire an unusual coordination number, greater than six. The present paper includes our extended studies on 1:1:1:1 Ln^{III} -NTA/EDTA/CDTA-SUA-PDA quaternary systems which have not yet been studied potentiometrically.

Experimental

Solutions of all the chemicals (A. R., B. D. H / E. Merck) were prepared in double-distilled water. Standard solutions of lanthanide nitrates were prepared and standardised^{4,5}. Solutions of di- and tri-potassium salts of NTA and EDTA/CDTA, respectively, were prepared by dissolving their calculated amounts in the required volume of potassium hydroxide. The concentrations of these solutions were further checked potentiometrically against 0.1 M KOH solution. All other solutions were prepared by direct-weighing method.

A Toshniwal CL46 digital pH meter with electrodes assembly was used and standardised